

Business Ethics and Economic Performance During the Recession at the U.S. Workplace

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 17 January 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Dr. Abulkasem Salem Dowa</p>	<p>This article examined ethics and compliance in small and large companies during a recession in a for-profit business sector by analyzing employees' perception of transparency and accountability in their companies. Ethical culture is more robust in large companies and is a critical factor that determines the maintenance of high level of business ethics during the recession for all companies large and small. The impact of a recession on the ethical behavior (business ethics) of, large companies are differing from that of small companies. During a recession, while misconduct and pressure to cut corners is lower for large companies, it is not the same for smaller companies. Together, these findings suggest that through national composite surveys indicate an overall high level the business ethics or lower misconduct during a recession, that might not be the trend considering business size.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Economic recession, Business ethics, Ethical culture, Ethical behavior, Economic Performance, U.S. Workplace.</p>	

INTRODUCTION

In tough economic times, there is a widespread understood that business ethics behaviors are expected to be declined, and a variety of unethical practices have emerged. Yet, in 2009, a survey data released by Ethics Resource Center (ERC) discovered that business ethics standards in the U.S workplace had been improved despite the economic downturn. Almost all the critical measures of ethical culture, such as observed misconduct, willingness to report observed misconduct, the strength of ethical culture, and perceived pressure to commit misconduct are increased compared to the ERC's last survey data in 2007 (NBES,2009). Quite frankly, the ERC board members were highly surprised by the surveys' findings. "We never expected to see findings like the once resulting from the 2009 update to our National Business Ethics Survey (NBES)" said Dr.Patricia J. Harned, ERC President (NBES, 2009). The results were just opposite what they anticipated to find out. Harned (2009), added," We expected to find plenty of negative trends. We were wrong and pleasantly surprised."

During the economic crisis. individuals would pay more attention to their corporate codes and policies of business ethics to face the emergence of heavy competition and stay in business. According to Sarah (2010), companies are more likely to support their employees in encouraging diligence because of the desire to keep the company out of trouble. Moreover, Harned (2009) pointed out that "The

anxieties of a shrinking economy did not translate, in general, into a free fall in ethical behavior p7.

In contrast, another survey conducted in December 2008 by the Health Care Compliance Association and Society of Corporate Compliance and Ethics HCCA indicated that the current economy significantly or somewhat increases the risk of compliance and ethics failures (HCCA, 2009). Nevertheless, ERC stated a different statement that despite the positive overall picture, there is a toll that the recession has taken on ethics in American busi-ness. NBES data showed, however, that the improvements tend to be temporary, and that management needs to stay alert as the economy gradually improves. Businesses and other organizations would return to business as usual (NBES, 2009). Therefore, Harned (2009) alerted that "the improvements in ethical conduct will be temporary. The focus needs to stay on ethical culture and the tone at the top, starting with an organization's directors and most senior executives."

Regardless of the effects were positive or negative, the survey findings have drawn our attention to examine the existed connection between the American financial growth and the workplace's ethical environment. The thought is that in a weak economic condition, workplace business ethics is tended to be raised. As Harned highlighted (NBES, 2009):

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“One of the largest surprises was the apparent link between the state of the nation’s economy and the strength of ethics in the workplace.”

Overall, the previous argument provides an essential sense of an existing correlation relationship between business ethics awareness and the state of the economy. This paper intends to determine the permanent connection between the two variables. The researcher is interested in investigating the state of workplace ethics during the economic recession cycle and the effects of the recession on workplace ethical behavior. To achieve this goal, the study will use the real Gross Domestic Production (GDP) as a dependent variable to represent the exchange rate of the economic growth in the U.S and the exchange of the three critical key measurers of ethical behavior which include observed misconduct, reporting of observed misconduct, and strength of ethical culture depends on variables to represent workplace ethics. Specifically, the study seeks to achieve the following:

- Figure out the current debate revolves the impacts of the recession on the workplace ethical loyalty.
- Describe the general tendency of the relationship between economic performance and business ethics status.
- Interpret the characteristics of the relationship between the two variables based on the statistics outcomes using the appropriate statistic instruments.
- The objective of the research is to improve understanding the effects of the recession on business ethics. Thus, the study aims to use the data which have been already collected by the ERC through it’s two years periodically survey questionnaire. The primary purpose of this paper is to develop a liable general relationship between economic growth and workplace business ethics.

Economic Recession: Black and White

The economic recession has been identified by many different scholars; all of them generally agree about the decline on the most critical national economy indexes. According to Neumann (2010), a recession is a significant decline in economic activity spread across the economy, lasting more than a few months, normally visible in real GDP, real income, employment, industrial production, and wholesale, retail sales. Whenever a recession takes a place, people start to be concerned about their business, profit, salary, jobs, and so on. During the last decade, the U.S economy has been hit by two separate cycles of a recession. The first cycle lasted eight months, from March 2001 through November, the second cycle which lasted 18 months, started from December 2007 through June 2009. Those two periods of the economic failure were involved the following characteristics:

1-Nation Economy Decline

The national economy and income usually are best described by the Gross Domestic Production (GDP). National Accounts Report (2009) identified GDP as final goods and services, that is, those purchased, credited, or otherwise, as; the final consumption of households, non-profit institutions serving households and government; fixed assets; and exports (minus imports). Table 1 generally reveals the significant decline of the U.S real GDP during the period from 2000 to 2009. Looking at the numbers, we recognize the significant changes every three years’ period time including the recession cycles. For example, during the period from 2000 to 2003, economic declines, the GDP fell from 4.1 to 2.5. However, the worst decline was in 2009, when the GDP reached as low as unfavorable 2.1. This was during 2007-2009 down economy. Figure 1 illustrates the average annual change from 2000 to 2009.

Table 1: The U.S Real GDP Per capita average annual change 2000-2009

Year	U.S Real GDP
2000	4.1
2003	2.5
2005	3.1
2007	1.9
2009	-2.6

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on BEA available data

Figure 1: The U.S Real GDP Per capita average annual change 2000-2009

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on BEA available data

2-Rising Unemployment Rate

Unemployment occurs when the demand for the labor force fall, causing numbers of layoffs and increasing the number of job seekers. In bad economic times, the unemployment rate continues to be up with rising in workforce supply.

3-Business Activities Are Down

Due to the economic downturn, consumers spent a tiny money than the one they used to. Consequently, the productivity and profitability the business are getting very slow.

On the positive side, despite the whole lousy picture, a weak economic has its benefits. First, interest rates always decrease during a bad economy, which is good for borrowers. Second, the inflation index goes down due to the lack in the demand of the goods, which is good for both savers and consumers*. (In the period of 2007-2009 recessions, inflation went up due to the increase in oil prices worldwide).

Business Ethics Key Categories

Ethics Resource Centre ERC identified the following four essential elements for measuring workplace ethical behaviors (ERC, 2010):

- 1- Observed misconduct at work: The employees’ ability to observe some significant unethical workplace behavior. Table 2 lists the most common types of misconduct observed by employees and the percentage of the U.S workforce during 2009-2007.
- 2- Reporting of observed misconduct (Whistleblowing): the employees’ commitment and willingness to report the misconduct if they observe it.
- 3-Strength of ethical culture: the business compliance and support for doing the right thing, such as practicing new laws,

regulations, and requirements that focus on ethical issues. ERC’s indexes of ethical culture include moral leadership, accountability, and values, as opposed to simply the rules or written ethics code.

4- Perceived pressure to commit misconduct (Pressure to cut corners): employees feel or perceive pressure to compromise ethics standards to achieve their jobs.

The Relationship between Business Ethics and Economic Growth During a Recession

We were looking at the numbers in table 2, we can reveal that the country had entered two periods of recession from 2000 to 2009. From 2000 through 2003, the GDP went down from 4.1 to 2.5, causing significant improvements in the critical elements of business ethics measures. For example, observed misconduct improved by fall with 9% from 55% in 2000 to 46% in 2003, reporting of observed misconduct increased by 8% from 56% to 64% in the same period, only the strength of ethical culture continued to be the same at 9%.

On the other hand, the data for 2007-2009 showed similarities to the period of 2000-2003. The real GDP recorded a negative decrease by reaching -2.6 % leading again to significant improvements in all business ethics key measures. Observed misconduct reduced by 7% from 56% in 2007 to 49% in 2009, reporting of observed misconduct rose by 4% from 59% to 63 at the same period, the strength of ethical culture doubled by 9% from 9% to 18%. All in all, the above data analysis supports the strong connection between both business ethics economic growth. The two, periods of the recession following the same manner, which is enough to emphasize the relationship. It shows that whenever economic growth falls, business ethics are getting better and better, and the relationship between both of them is generally negative.

Table 2: Fundamental changes on the most business ethics key measures 2000-2009

Year	Observed Misconduct	Reporting of Observed Misconduct	Strength of Ethical Culture	The U.S Real GDP
2000	55%	56%	9%	4.1%
2003	46%	64%	9%	2.5%
2005	52%	53%	10%	3.1%
2007	56%	59%	9%	1.9%
2009	49%	63%	18%	-2.6%

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on ERC available data

Figure 2: Fundamental changes of the most business ethics key measures 2000-2009

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on ERC available data

CONCLUSION

The researcher presented his opinion in supporting the connection between improving workplace ethical behavior and the decline in economic growth on times of crisis. This study is assuming being the first empirical study attempts to develop a general relationship between workplace ethical awareness and economic growth, particularly in times of economic turmoil. Bad economic times would encourage people to work harder and review their businesses in terms of many aspects of the entire business environment, including the state of ethics. As a result, companies are likely to be aware of their ethical culture in times of crisis more than any other time to survive. By comparing two different significant periods of a recession, 2000-2003 and 2007-2009, the study found out that during the economic crisis, business ethics were more likely to increase, and ethical culture seemed to grow up and become more assertive. The study also proves an existing strong relationship between economic growth and workplace ethics, and it is usually harmful. In their future research, the researcher intends to develop a mathematical model to measure the relationship and the correlation between the two variables. The regression equation will be used for the

model; data for the study will be obtained from the ERC, national ethics two years’ survey.

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